

DFN Modelling Workshop for Nuclear Waste Repositories – 9th –12th of June 2026

Tuesday, 9 June 2026 - Friday, 12 June 2026

Sweden, Uppsala Universitet, Ångströmlaboratoriet

Book of Abstracts

Contents

Simulating DFNs and fracture-scale processes using OpenGeoSys	1
An introduction to PorePy for flow simulations	1
Hydraulic Fracturing by Supercritical CO2 Injection Considering Rock Microstructure	1
Fracture Trace-Constrained Conditional Simulation for 3D Fracture Network Extrapolation: Application to Nuclear Waste Repository Development	2
FracLab: A Robust 3D DFN Generator for Coupled Process Modelling for Fractured Media	2
Challenges of DFN Generation in Complex Geological Models: The Äspö HRL Example	3
Fracture Orientation Uncertainty is Your Friend! (Provided it is Thoroughly Evaluated)	3
Numerical simulation of damage evolution around the PF/PF-A experiment borehole in faulted Opalinus Clay	4
From classical DFN flow problems to coupled thermal-hydrological and transport chal- lenges	4
Hydro-mechanical coupling in deposition tunnels	5
Bridging DFN and impact of operational phase modelling	5
From fracture data to DFN for the Safety Case	6
Evaluating DFN Generation Methods for Fracture Network Topology in Crystalline Rock	6
Input Data for DFN Modelling: Research Data and Deterministic Modelling	7

Demos/Hackathons / 2

Simulating DFNs and fracture-scale processes using OpenGeoSys

Authors: Thomas Nagel¹; Mostafa Mollaali¹

¹ *TU Bergakademie Freiberg*

We will go through examples for simulating flow and transport in stressed fractures using OpenGeoSys. This will be done in a browser-based setting, so no prior installation is required this time. The examples include

- pathway-dominated flow through a rough fracture
- brittle fracture propagation in triaxial stress states using phase-field models

Other examples are available. Participants can put their focus according to their interest.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

3 hours

Demos/Hackathons / 3

An introduction to PorePy for flow simulations

Author: Eirik Keilegavlen¹

¹ *University of Bergen*

We give an introduction to the open-source research software PorePy, which is a multiphysics simulation framework primarily aimed at fractured porous media. PorePy provides (semi)automatic mesh generation for complex fracture networks and comes with a set of multiphysics simulation setups that are ready to run and can easily be adapted to user demands. The framework emphasizes robust formulations and numerical methods and aims to faithfully follow the mathematical description of the governing processes (e.g., conservation of mass). PorePy is in part built as a library, where some parts (e.g. meshing) can be extracted and combined with other software in wider workflows.

For the demonstration, we will provide jupyter notebooks that allow users to get going with setting up PorePy simulations, targeting flow and transport processes in DFN geometries. The material will be made available through GitHub Codespaces (which require only a GitHub account, no local installation) and through a Docker container. A script for local installations on Linux systems can also be made available.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Preferred length is 2 hours; can be shortened (somewhat) and lengthened depending on wider organizational requirements.

Presentations / 4

Hydraulic Fracturing by Supercritical CO₂ Injection Considering Rock Microstructure

Author: Weihong Yuan^{None}

Co-authors: Keita Yoshioka ; Tao You

Supercritical CO₂ fracturing is expected to create more complex fracture networks than water-based counterparts, thereby improving the permeability and heat extraction in geothermal reservoirs. The underlying fracture mechanisms driven by this low-viscosity fluid may differ from conventional hydraulic fracturing. In this study, we develop a stabilized hydromechanical phase-field fracture model to simulate hydraulic fracturing in two- and three-dimensional polycrystalline microstructures. To address numerical instabilities caused by strong heterogeneity and operator splitting, we propose a novel spatial stabilization term for the monolithic solution of the coupled hydromechanical problem. We then conduct numerical simulations of hydraulic fracture evolution considering rock microstructure under water and supercritical CO₂ injection. Our numerical results reproduce laboratory observations and demonstrate that the generation of complex fracture networks is controlled by both rock heterogeneity and fracturing fluid. Our findings further confirm that supercritical CO₂ fracturing is more likely to trigger remote activation of heterogeneous interfaces, leading to more complex fracture morphologies.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 5

Fracture Trace-Constrained Conditional Simulation for 3D Fracture Network Extrapolation: Application to Nuclear Waste Repository Development

Authors: Chuanyin Jiang¹; Auli Niemi¹; Joel Geier¹; Qinghua Lei¹; Chin-Fu Tsang¹

¹ *Uppsala University*

Accurate representation of 3D fracture networks is fundamental to risk assessment and design optimization in underground engineering, especially for nuclear waste geological disposal projects where positioning of deposition holes in tunnels is a major issue. This work presents a new conditional simulation framework for trace-constrained DFN extrapolation. A systematic classification of fracture-observation object intersection types is proposed, and case-specific conditioning strategies are developed to enhance the adaptability and accuracy of the simulation. To verify the framework, a synthetic reference DFN resembling real repository conditions is considered, and a step-wise conditioning approach that mimics the progressive availability of fracture trace data during actual construction processes is examined. Results demonstrate that the proposed framework not only strictly honors the observed trace data but also maintains the global and local statistical characteristics of fractures. Importantly, the progressive integration of conditioning data significantly reduces the uncertainty in determining spatial distributions of large fractures. This framework offers a practical and efficient tool for DFN extrapolation, supporting subsequent groundwater inflow assessment and deposition-hole siting decisions in the development of deep geological disposal of nuclear waste.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 6

FracLab: A Robust 3D DFN Generator for Coupled Process Modelling for Fractured Media

Authors: Chuanyin Jiang¹; Qinghua Lei¹

¹ *Uppsala University*

We developed FracLab, a robust and powerful 3D discrete fracture network (DFN) generator for high-quality fracture networks, which can enable complex numerical simulation of coupled processes. FracLab incorporates optimized geometry trimming and enhanced rejection criteria to generate high-quality 3D DFNs, enabling robust mesh generation for both fractures and rock matrices; it also regulates minimum element size, reduces mesh element count, and improves mesh quality via full-domain geometry optimization, thereby enabling efficient 3D multiphysics simulations that can capture nonlinear geomechanical deformations, local stress variations, fracture-matrix interactions, and stress-dependent fluid flow and solute transport in densely fractured media.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 7

Challenges of DFN Generation in Complex Geological Models: The Äspö HRL Example

Author: Anne Gehrke^{None}

This presentation describes the generation of a discrete fracture network (DFN) model for the Äspö Hard Rock Laboratory based on geological and structural data published by SKB. A three-dimensional geological model derived from SKB site descriptive reports provides the structural framework for DFN construction. Fracture sets are generated consistently with this model and used to derive an equivalent porous medium for groundwater flow simulations with the code d3f++. The contribution focuses on the modelling workflow and on challenges arising from the complex geological geometry and its impact on DFN generation.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 8

Fracture Orientation Uncertainty is Your Friend! (Provided it is Thoroughly Evaluated)

Author: Martin Stigsson¹

¹ SKB

As a modeller of discrete fracture network models, one usually gets tables with given orientation data gathered by mapping geologists. Seldom these data are questioned by the modeller but rather taken as definite. This may lead to spurious inferences and hence fracture models that do not accurately reflect the true condition of the rock mass.

Uncertainties are not only stemming from tool imprecision, but to a larger extent from external disturbances and human factors. By systematically identifying all relevant sources of uncertainty, that may affect the measured value, and estimate their individual contributions, it is possible to infer an aggregated probability space of the orientation for each single object. This can be expressed as a rough one-parameter dihedral angle measure, Ω , or as a non-parametric surface on a lower hemisphere stereonet, X .

The one-parameter representation is well suited for the analysis of large datasets, e.g. to discriminate observations with large uncertainty. In contrast, the non-parametric visualization is useful when examining individual or a few structures that e.g. are in conflict with the established conceptual understanding of the rock mass. The uncertainties may also be used for inverse modelling workflows to evaluate more accurate input parameters for fracture network models.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

20 minutes

Presentations / 9**Numerical simulation of damage evolution around the PF/PF-A experiment borehole in faulted Opalinus Clay****Authors:** Muhammad Raharsya Andiva¹; Qinghua Lei¹; Chenxi Zhao²; Martin Ziegler³¹ *Uppsala University*² *CCTEG Coal Mining Research Institute*³ *Federal Office of Topography (swisstopo)*

The Progressive Failure (PF/PF-A) Experiment at the Mont Terri Underground Rock Laboratory offers a unique opportunity to investigate damage evolution around underground openings in faulted Opalinus Clay under in-situ stress conditions. We present a 3D numerical modelling framework developed to simulate progressive failure in structurally complex clay shale and its long-term evolution subject to hydro-mechanical effects. The approach integrates a site-constrained discrete fracture network, explicit fault zone representation, and anisotropic material behaviour within a discontinuum formulation to capture structurally controlled damage processes around an experiment borehole. The simulations capture stress redistribution, fracture reactivation, and the emergence of a characteristic inner-outer damage zone structure governed by fault–fracture interactions and structural orientation. Sensitivity analyses demonstrate the importance of fault–borehole geometry in controlling damage localisation and extent. Ongoing model developments incorporate coupled hydro-mechanical processes, including suction-driven desaturation and effective stress evolution, to better represent the experimental conditions. Preliminary coupled simulation results indicate that hydraulic effects significantly influence near-borehole damage initiation and spatial distribution. Our modelling framework provides a physics-based tool for interpreting PF/PF-A experimental observations, with important implications for the safe design and performance assessment of nuclear waste disposal in Opalinus Clay.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:**Presentations / 10****From classical DFN flow problems to coupled thermal-hydrological and transport challenges****Author:** Andrew Frampton¹¹ *Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, Sweden*

Modelling flow and transport in discrete fracture networks (DFNs) has developed considerably over the past decades, yet the field continues to be reshaped by new conceptual challenges, computational advances, and emerging applications. This talk provides a personal perspective on the evolution of DFN modelling, from foundational concepts to current challenges and future directions.

A central theme is flow channelling and transport using a Lagrangian framework, where particle travel times and transport resistance provide intuitive measures of transport variability and solute retention in fractured rock. Results from stochastic DFN ensembles highlight how fracture connectivity and small-scale heterogeneity can produce early arrivals, long-tailed breakthrough behaviour, and large variability between network realisations that conventional continuum approaches often fail to capture.

A second theme concerns coupled thermal-hydrological freeze-thaw processes relevant to future cold-climate conditions. Seasonal permafrost dynamics and glacial loading can strongly alter groundwater flow, transport pathways, and fracture properties over timescales ranging from seasons to glacial cycles.

The talk concludes with perspectives on key open challenges, including internal fracture heterogeneity, coupled TH/THM processes, and stochastic upscaling of flow and transport in fractured rock systems.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 11

Hydro-mechanical coupling in deposition tunnels

Author: Brandon Stock¹

Co-author: Andrew Frampton²

¹ *Stockholm University*

² *Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, Sweden*

Water inflow into subsurface excavations in crystalline fractured rock is a complex problem, largely due to hydromechanical coupled processes associated with excavation. Field experiments can exhibit scale effects, where inflow into excavations can be less than predicted based on observations from smaller diameter holes. This work uses a recent study examining flow through a single fracture subject to normal loading, which indicates a stress dependent reduction in transmissivity. This relationship is implemented within a small scale DFN model representing a deposition tunnel/hole. The approach includes spatial variations in stress induced by excavation, allowing transmissivity to evolve as a function of normal stress acting on individual fractures. Stress normal to individual fractures is calculated and transmissivity corrections are applied based on the local stress state. These corrections depend both on fracture orientation and the in-situ stress field. A range of realisations are used to evaluate the ability of this approach to predicting inflow into deposition tunnels accounting for the excavation influence zone. In addition, the impact of internal transmissivity heterogeneity is investigated compared against the conventional assumption of uniform in-plane transmissivity. The results aim to clarify whether stress dependent transmissivity improves inflow predictions when upscaling from boreholes to larger excavations.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 12

Bridging DFN and impact of operational phase modelling

Author: Virve Iisalmi¹

¹ *Posiva Oy*

DFN modelling has been extensively used in Posiva's safety case to represent fracture-controlled flow and transport across scales, capturing system behavior with a high level of complexity and detail. However, its computational demands limit its applicability in operational decision-making during the repository lifecycle. In contrast, current modelling on impact of construction and operations relies on simplified, site-scale representations, with local heterogeneity incorporated as observed. While this enables efficient simulations and supports operational use, it leaves uncertainties in unobserved regions and provides limited resolution both at site scale and between known fracture zones.

DFN modelling is therefore needed to extend heterogeneity into less constrained regions and to provide the level of detail required for tunnel section scale analysis. The key challenge is to integrate DFN approaches into the workflow in a sufficiently lightweight and practical manner to support routine predictions and decision-making.

This presentation introduces a synthetic example of a tunnel section scale situation requiring modelling input to support operational decision-making. To begin, conservative assumptions are used to approximate transport-relevant geometries. The central question to the group is whether DFN modelling could be applied in a lightweight way to better represent these conditions and improve the solution.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

20 min presentation

Presentations / 13

From fracture data to DFN for the Safety Case

Author: Antti Poteri^{None}

DFN-based modelling is essential for capturing the heterogeneity of the bedrock and enabling credible mechanical, flow, and transport modelling of the site. This presentation examines how fracture data are translated into discrete fracture network (DFN) models to support the safety case for a geological repository, with a focus on flow and transport pathways in fractured rock. The central challenge is not only to describe fracture geometry, but also to determine which fractures are hydraulically connected and actively carry flow. The application of DFN modelling at Olkiluoto is illustrated through examples from Posiva's latest safety case.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 14

Evaluating DFN Generation Methods for Fracture Network Topology in Crystalline Rock

Author: Sarah Wehmann¹

¹ *Chair of Repository Safety, RWTH Aachen University*

Numerical subsurface models rely on relevant input data and modelling methods to generate robust representations of fluid flow in fractured rock systems.

In this study, a comprehensive discrete fracture network (DFN) modelling workflow is developed using photogrammetric data acquired from an open-pit mine in a crystalline complex in Germany. Several DFN generation methods (tracemap extrusion, fracture growth, geometric) are applied and compared with the aim of identifying the most suitable approach for representing fracture network topology, which is a key control on fluid flow in crystalline rocks.

The results highlight how alternative modelling approaches influence the resulting network topology and, consequently, the representation of connectivity in three-dimensional space.

This presentation aims to initiate discussion on key challenges in DFN modelling, particularly regarding fracture network topology, the conversion of two-dimensional observations into three-dimensional representations, and the strengths and limitations of available software tools.

Publication: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00295450.2025.2581510#d1e514>

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon:

Presentations / 15

Input Data for DFN Modelling: Research Data and Deterministic Modelling

Author: Antti Joutsen¹

¹ *Posiva*

This presentation examines how research data is used for deterministic models, which act as input information in Discrete Fracture Network (DFN) modelling. It highlights how geological, hydrogeological and geophysical observations and measurements are interpreted, structured, and translated into deterministic representations, forming the basis for DFN generation.

Preferred duration for demo/hackathon: